

ABSTRACT BOOK

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"DATA-DRIVEN ENVIRONMENTAL DECISION-MAKING"

the water hardness simultaneously, and that Shapley values are a versatile and useful alternative for gene ranking, providing insight into the importance of individual genes.

1.05.P Epigenetic Changes Modulating the Response of Organisms to Environmental Challenges: From Phenotypic Effects to Microevolution Patterns

1.05.P-Th012 Incorporating Epigenetics in Adverse Outcome Pathways: The EPIBOOST Project

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Lately, environmental studies started appraising several 'omics, e.g., epigenomics, as remarkable tools to improve Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) frameworks. Besides the mechanistic enlightening of toxicity that these 'omics can provide in general, the discovery of molecular initiating events and molecular pathways for adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) is promoted. While epigenetic modifications are likely primary molecular initiating events as per their role in constraining gene expression, there are still important challenges to overcome in order to incorporate epigenomics into regulatory frameworks, especially because consistent links to effects at the level of the phenotype (and then to higher levels of biological organization for improved ecological relevance) are yet to be established, as well as are trends and parallels across species. This is the foundation of the EPIBOOST research, a project addressing environmental epigenetics concerning aquatic organisms and model pollutants. EPIBOOST will focus on AOPs initiated by DNA methylation in model freshwater and marine organisms (microalgae, microcrustaceans, and fish), exposed to three model chemicals representing persistent or emerging threats nowadays or in the near future (metals, antibiotics, and toxins). Briefly, samples will be screened for global methylation and analysed via whole-genome bisulfite sequencing. Gene expression will be assessed via targeted or untargeted approaches to understand whether gene expression correlates to the changes in the epigenome. Phenotypic effects ranging from the subcellular to the population level will be assessed in parallel concerning specific (e.g., photosynthetic efficiency, neurotoxicity) and more general (e.g., growth rates, behaviour) responses to stress. Such a comprehensive approach will allow a meaningful insight on the AOPs for the selected model contaminants in the aquatic compartment, and particularly support the validation of epigenetic modifications as robust molecular initiating events.

1.05.P-Th013 Time- and Dose-Dependent DNA Methylation Changes in Earthworms Exposed to Cadmium: Genome Wide and Gene-Specific Epigenetic Perspective

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The heavy metal cadmium (Cd) can cause DNA hypermethylation, which has already been demonstrated in many invertebrates, including earthworms. However, detailed characterisation of DNA methylation landscape upon Cd exposure, as well as mechanisms behind the DNA hypermethylation, are still largely unexplored. Therefore, in this study, we used the earthworm model *Lumbricus terrestris* to explore time- and dose-dependent effects of Cd on global, genome wide, and gene-specific DNA methylation and its underlying mechanisms. Earthworms were exposed to two Cd concentrations (10 and 25 mg/kg) for a period of 12 weeks and sampled at several time points (1, 2, 4, 12 weeks). Global cytosine hypermethylation was revealed using specific antibodies in dot blots, whereas bsRADseq was used to determine genome wide DNA methylation changes and pinpoint specific genomic regions mostly affected by Cd exposure. To study the underlying mechanisms, we determined the gene expression as well as the activity of DNA methylation and demethylation components like DNA methyltransferases (DNMT1 and 3), and ten-eleven translocation (TET) genes. However, neither gene expression nor DNMT and TET enzyme activity showed significant differences in the Cd exposure groups. More specifically, we focused on the gene body methylation (gbm) of metallothionein 2 (MT2), one of the most important Cd detoxification proteins. Using bisulfite conversion and sequencing we were able to detect some changes in MT2 gbm; however, these changes could not be correlated to MT2 gene expression. The results of this study demonstrate the importance of studying epigenetic marks and underlying mechanisms in organisms under pollution pressure and point to missing links, which need to be further explored.

1.05.P-Th014 Multigenerational DNA Methylation Patterns Following Copper Exposure in *Daphnia*: The Role of Exposure History

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Epigenetic mechanisms are moving to the forefront of environmental sciences because of their key role in shaping gene-environment interactions, phenotypic plasticity, and evolutionary responses. Specifically, environmentally induced DNA methylation changes are known to shape biological responses to chemical contamination, and the transgenerational inheritance of methylation marks across nonexposed generations has been confirmed in invertebrate and vertebrate species. Here, we focused on the freshwater invertebrate *Daphnia magna*, with the goal of further understanding the involvement of DNA methylation in their response and eventual adaptation to copper contamination. To do so, we specifically tested the hypothesis that different histories

of exposure to Cu could determine different epigenetic signatures, which would be carried on into nonexposed generations. Accordingly, daphnids with different histories of past exposure to Cu were exposed to toxic levels of the metal for one generation (F0) and then monitored for three subsequent unexposed generations (F1, F2, and F3), with copper-induced DNA methylation changes, their potential transgenerational inheritance, and life-history traits being recorded. Overall, DNA methylation changes targeted important genes for counteracting the effects of metals and oxidative stress, including *dynein light chain*, *ribosomal kinase*, and *nuclear fragile X mental retardation-interacting protein*. Also, contrasting overall and gene-specific methylation responses were observed in organisms differing in their exposure history to Cu, with different transgenerational methylation responses being also identified among the two groups, without apparent life-history costs. Overall, results confirmed the capacity of Cu to promote DNA methylation transgenerational inheritance in a manner related explicitly to the history of exposure, thereby highlighting the potential for the development and incorporation of epigenetic biomarkers in risk assessment frameworks.

1.05.P-Th015 Transgenerational Transcriptional Responses in *Daphnia magna*: The Role of Copper Exposure History
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Chemical exposures can extend their effects beyond “directly” exposed generations and influence the offspring response to future stressors. Thus, the establishment of transgenerational effects is a powerful phenomenon holding beyond exposure periods. Here, we assessed the transgenerational effects after Cu exposure in the invertebrate *D. magna* at the transcriptional level, while also evaluating the influence of acclimation history on such responses. To do so, daphnids with different histories of exposure, i.e., organisms acclimated in a Cu-enriched medium vs. blank ASTM for three generations, were exposed for one generation (F0) to an elevated concentration of the metal, and then the transcriptional response from F0 and F3 (F3 is the first truly unexposed generation) was inspected by real-time PCR employing an array with 41 genes (involved in detoxification and antioxidant response, DNA damage repair, circadian rhythm, and epigenetic regulation). Results showed that daphnids with different histories of exposure to Cu presented distinct transcriptional profiles at F0 and F3, with nonacclimated organisms showing higher modulation on gene expression. Despite the different exposure histories, histone modifier genes were always found to be transcriptionally altered in F0 and F3, suggesting the involvement of histone modifications in the response of *D. magna* to metal exposure. Besides, markedly distinct transgenerational transcriptional responses were found between the two groups of organisms, with nonacclimated daphnids showing a greater number of genes with modulated expression. Overall, results confirmed the influence of exposure history on transcriptional responses, and the ability of metals to determine transgenerational transcriptional responses across non-exposed generations.

1.05.P-Th016 Marine Pollutant Tributyltin Affects DNA Methylation and Fitness of Banded Murex (*Hexaplex trunculus*) Populations

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Banded murex, *Hexaplex trunculus*, is a marine gastropod whose reproductive fitness can be severely affected by very low concentrations of antifouling compound tributyl-tin (TBT). Tributyl-tin has a strong xenoandrogen impact on snails, causing development of imposex (e.g., superimposition of male sexual characteristic in females), thereby affecting the fitness of entire populations. Tributyl-tin is also known as a DNA demethylating agent and an obesogenic factor. The aim of this study was to unravel the interactions between TBT bioaccumulation, phenotypic responses, and epigenetic and genetic endpoints in native populations of murex snail *H. trunculus*. Seven populations inhabiting environments along the pollution gradient were sampled in the coastal eastern Adriatic. Those included sites of intense marine traffic and boat maintenance activity, and sites with low anthropogenic impact. Populations inhabiting intermediately and highly polluted sites exhibited higher TBT burden, higher incidence of imposex, and higher wet mass of snails than populations on low polluted sites. Other morphometric traits and cellular biomarker responses did not show clear differentiation among populations in relation to the marine traffic/pollution intensity. Analysis of methylation sensitive amplification polymorphism (MSAP) revealed environmentally driven population differentiation and higher epigenetic than genetic within-population diversity. Moreover, decrease in genome-wide DNA methylation coincided with the imposex level as well as with the snail mass, suggesting epigenetic background of animal phenotypic response.

1.05.P-Th017 Genotoxicity and Epigenotoxicity of CMIT/MIT on *Daphnia magna*: Trans- and Multigenerational Effects
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CMIT/MIT (the mixture of 5-chloro-2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one and 2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one) is the biocide consistently detected in the aquatic environment due to its broad-spectrum usage in various industrial fields. The ecotoxicological information of CMIT/MIT is very limited to within-generational toxicity evaluation, though multigenerational exposure frequently occurred. Furthermore, despite a possible role of epigenetics on genotoxicity, their relationship is poorly known in the ecotoxicological context. For that reason, we investigated whether parental (PE) and multigenerational exposure (ME) of CMIT/MIT led trans- and/or multigenerational effects by measuring various phenotypic biomarkers over four consecutive generations. Genotoxicity and epigenotoxicity of CMIT/MIT in *Daphnia magna* were also examined using the Comet assay and global DNA methylation. Our results showed the deleterious effects of CMIT/MIT at various endpoints of *Daphnia*, which had experienced the different exposure histories. Parental effects in the PE scenario can be transgenerational or recovered after the termination of exposure.

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Epigenetics is at the forefront of environmental sciences, since environmentally induced epigenetic changes can shape biological responses to chemical contamination

Hypothesis

Different histories of exposure to copper (Cu) could determine different epigenetic signatures, which would be carried on into non-exposed generations

Aim

Assess copper-induced DNA methylation changes, potential transgenerational inheritance and life-history traits

TAKEAWAY

- Copper promoted epigenetic transgenerational inheritance consistently reflecting history of exposure.
- Life-history responses reflected consistently the epigenetic effects of Cu and the history of exposure to the stressor, providing a link between DNA methylation and phenotypic effects.
- The results support the development and incorporation of epigenetic biomarkers into risk assessment frameworks

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